

Development of a Data and Analytics Infrastructure for Total Exposure Health Research

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Topic: Early Research in Total Exposure Health

Abstract:

Comprehensive quantification of effects of the modern environment on health requires taking into account data from all contributing environmental exposures (*exposome*) which can span endogenous processes within the body, biological responses of adaptation to environment, physiological manifestations of these responses, and socio-behavioral factors. Exposomic research is translational in nature as the exposome includes direct biological pathway alterations as well as mutagenic and epigenetic mechanisms of environmental influences on the phenome. Generating exposomes requires integration of data from wearable and stationary sensors, environmental monitors, personal activities, physiology, medication use and other clinical data, genomic and other biospecimen-derived, person-reported and computational models. Processes to support this aggregation and integration must accommodate variable spatio-temporal resolutions and account for multiple study, experimental and analytical designs. Gaps in measured data may need to be filled with modeled data along with characterization of uncertainties.

We are developing a scalable informatics infrastructure, Exposure Health Informatics Ecosystem (EHIE), derived from federally funded National Institutes of Health's (NIH) National Institute of Biomedical Imaging and Bioengineering (NIBIB) Pediatric Research Using Integrated Sensor Monitoring Systems (PRISMS) program, and addresses these needs at scale, incorporating the latest Big Data approaches. The infrastructure is a comprehensive, standards-based, open-source informatics platform that provides semantically consistent, metadata-driven, event-based management of exposomic data. Using an event-driven architecture allows the modeling and storage of all activities related to the study itself and its operations in their primitive form on a timeline as events that can be transformed to higher/analytical models based on use-cases. Moreover its implementation using advanced graph and document store technologies limits semantic dissonance and enables the use of novel big data approaches in a natural way. EHIE is aligned with the goals of modern environmental health research supporting meaningful integration of sensor and biomedical data. It currently consists of the following components:

1. Data acquisition pipeline: Hardware and software tools, wireless networking, and protocols to support easy sensor system deployment, and robust sensor data collection.
2. Participant facing tools: Collect and annotate a variety of patient reported and activity data, as well as inform and provide feedback to study participants on their current clinical and environmental status.
3. Researcher facing platforms: Tools and processes for researchers undertaking exposomic studies for a variety of experimental designs or for clinical care.
4. Computational modeling: Generate comprehensive spatio-temporal data in the absence of measurements and for recognition of activity signatures from sensor measurements.

5. Central *big data* federation/integration platform: Standards-based, open-access infrastructure that integrates measured and computationally modeled data with biomedical information along with characterizing uncertainties associated with using these data.

Using this component-based ecosystem we are able to support the deployment and performance of sensor-based studies, and the integration, processing, visualization, and secure transmission of study data for most research designs. EHIE provides an effective, flexible and open access approach to collecting, managing and analyzing high-resolution data from sensors. Because the infrastructure is based on logical data models for clinically relevant exposomes (environmental exposures such as air quality, which have health impacts), the infrastructure is flexible and adaptable to many scenarios. The infrastructure also provides mechanisms for integrating exposure profiles (exposomes) with clinical, self-reported, behavioral, and other research data. EHIE provides key infrastructure that can accommodate diverse types of future studies that include general and personal environmental exposure monitoring, activities, and physiological responses to the environment. In addition, EHIE supports supplementation of direct measurements with computationally modeled data for exposures, activities and locations that can easily be assimilated into comprehensive spatio-temporal records.

We are establishing a Center of Excellence for Exposure Health Informatics (CEEHI) that will serve as a collaborative for continuing investigations and development of state-of-the-art informatics methods for exposomics. CEEHI will seek to advance the use of an ultra large scale infrastructure for integrated sensor monitoring systems, advance the use of novel sensors, and support the management of research processes and data for activities related to the study and its operations. It will serve as a go-to center for researchers interested in conducting sensor-based, mobile and virtual studies that include measurements of the environment, physiology and behavior of participants by provide expertise, guidance, infrastructure and other resources to the University research community and external groups.

In this presentation, we discuss the original EHIE architecture, and its evolution towards a generalizable multi-scale and multi-omics platform providing robust pipelines for reproducible exposomic research, and results from pilot projects using real-time, low-cost air quality sensors to provide spatio-temporal records of particulate matter exposures. These studies are aligned with the NIH Environmental influences on Child Health Outcomes (ECHO) and NIH PRISMS programs and evaluated participant acceptance of personal and home-based *Internet-of-Things* sensor monitoring; demonstrated the feasibility of gathering environmental exposure data from low-cost sensors at a very fine levels of resolution; and demonstrated the efficacy in integrating heterogeneous data for building and analyzing exposure profiles. In these pilots we have integrated over 25 million and 5 million environmental (indoor and outdoor) as well as clinical events respectively as a timeline of events that supports triggering and management of study interventions, and transformations to higher/analytical models for ongoing study analysis. We conclude this presentation with a discussion on CEEHI and how it can provide infrastructural support for future exposure health studies.

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